

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoly carbamides

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Abstract : Seven novel 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoly carbamides were synthesised by interacting 1-naphthyl isocyanate and various 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoles. The identities of these newly synthesised carbamides have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectral studies and screened for their possible antimicrobial activity to get potent bioactive molecule.

Keywords : 1-Naphthyl isocyanate, hydrazino benzothiazoles, naphthyl hydrazino benzothiazoly carbamides, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Benzothiazole derivatives have been studied extensively and found to have diverse chemical reactivity and broad spectrum of biological activity¹⁻⁴. Keeping this in view, a certain new derivatives were synthesized taking benzothiazole as the basic moiety. Isocyanates are important intermediates and the high yields and lack of byproducts with this type of reaction have led to their commercial exploitation in pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals and in the polymer field. Encouraged by these observations, and in continuation of our search for pharmacologically potential benzothiazole derivatives, we synthesised some new title compounds and screen them for their possible antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

Herein, we report the synthesis of 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoly carbamides (**3a**) by interaction of 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoles (**1a**) and 1-naphthyl isocyanate (**2**) in acetone medium. After condensation the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether to afford a light coloured solid. The product was purified by chloroform-petroleum ether. Similarly, the related 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoly carbamides **3(b-g)** were obtained when 1-naphthyl isocyanate (**2**) interacts with other 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoles **1(b-g)**.

All products were crystallised from ethanol before recording the physical data (Table 1). The purity of compounds were checked by TLC. The spectral analysis⁵⁻⁷ IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectra of the product were observed. Optical rotation of the product was also recorded.

Experimental

The reagent grade chemicals were obtained from commercial sources and purified by either distillation or recrystallization before use. Melting points of all synthesized compounds were determined using open capillary tube on Mac digital melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in solid phase KBr disks on Shimadzu IR affinity-1 FTIR spectrometer and ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 on Bruker DRX-300 of NMR spectrometer 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on Waters UPLC-TQD Mass Spectrometer having ionization mode ES^+ , sample dilution made in methanol, mobile phase was used ACN : water (90 : 10) at flow rate – 0.2 ml/min. Optical rotations were measured on Equip-Tronics EQ 800 Digital Polarimeter in CHCl_3 . Purity of synthesized compounds has been checked by thin layer chromatography. It was performed on E. Merck precoated silica gel plates.

General procedure :

Preparation of 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoles :

Concentrate HCl (1 mL) was added drop wise to hy-

Table 1. Physical characterisation of 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamides **3(a-g)** (Scheme 2)

Sr. no.	Compd.	Yield g (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Req.)		$[\alpha]_D^{31}$ (c, CHCl ₃)	R_f (4 : 6, EtOAc : pet. ether)
				N	S		
1.	3a	2.1 (64.63)	258–260	15.34 (16.76)	9.33 (9.58)	+115° (0.93)	0.43
2.	3b	2.8 (87.24)	239–241	14.98 (15.19)	8.11 (8.68)	+220° (0.96)	0.67
3.	3c	2.8 (88.56)	245–247	14.33 (15.19)	8.15 (8.68)	+78.43° (0.95)	0.58
4.	3d	2.6 (81.47)	219–221	14.24 (15.19)	8.09 (8.68)	+180° (0.92)	0.64
5.	3e	2.0 (62.39)	258–261	15.75 (16.09)	8.65 (9.19)	+140° (0.98)	0.70
6.	3f	2.5 (78.13)	210–212	15.99 (16.09)	8.90 (9.19)	+170° (0.94)	0.52
7.	3g	2.4 (73.98)	231–233	15.83 (16.09)	8.82 (9.19)	+260° (0.95)	0.63

drazine hydrate (0.2 mol, 1 mL 80%) at 5–10 °C followed by ethylene glycol (20 mL). To the above solution 2-aminobenzothiazole (0.01 mol, 1.85 g) was added in portions. It was then refluxed for 3 h, cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. Similarly, various substituted 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazoles were prepared **1(a-g)** (Scheme 1).

Preparation of 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamides :

1-Naphthyl isocyanate (0.01 M, 1.6 mL) was mixed with acetone solution of 2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazole (0.01 M, 1.65 g in 10 mL), and mixture after shaking for sometime was kept at room temperature for 24 h. Acetone was distilled off to obtained sticky residue. This residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether to afford a light coloured solid. Similarly, other carbamides were synthesised **3(a-g)** (Scheme 2).

Spectral data :

1-Naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamide (3a) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3278 (N-H stretch), 3049 (Ar-H stretch), 1635 (C=O), 1556 (N-H bend), 1396 (C-N), 705 (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm) : δ 8.64–7.35 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.83–5.68 (3H, m, NH), 7.45–6.12 (7H, m, naphthyl protons); Mass (*m/z*) : 335 (M+1), 313, 299,

286, 284, 229, 206, 202, 187, 170 (Found : C, 64.26; H, 4.06; N, 15.34; S, 9.33. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄N₄SO : C, 65.67; H, 4.19; N, 16.76; S, 9.58%).

1-Naphthyl-2-hydrazino-4-chloro-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamide (3b) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3269 (N-H stretch), 3059 (Ar-H stretch), 1712 (C=O), 1641 (C=N), 1546 (N-H bend), 1294 (C-N), 721 (C-S), 788 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm) : δ 8.732–7.356 (7H, m, naphthyl protons), 7.260–6.207 (3H, m, Ar-H), 5.662–4.925 (2H, m, NH), 4.925–3.60 (1H, s, NH); Mass (*m/z*) : 409, 242, 240, 183 (Found : C, 58.47; H, 3.38; N, 14.98; S, 8.11. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃N₄SOCl : C, 58.61; H, 3.52; N, 15.19; S, 8.68 %).

1-Naphthyl-2-hydrazino-4-methyl-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamide (3e) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3269 (N-H stretch), 3049 (Ar-H stretch), 2920 (sp³ C-H stretch), 1728 (C=O), 1635 (C=N), 1554 (N-H bend), 1342 (C-N), 731 (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm) : δ 8.253–7.783 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.757–7.247 (7H, m, naphthyl protons), 2.886–2.614 (2H, m, NH), 2.461–2.418 (1H, s, NH), 1.40–1.293 (3H, s, CH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 354, 335, 313, 298, 285, 220, 202, 187 (Found : C, 64.32; H, 4.34; N, 15.75; S, 8.65. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₆N₄SO : C, 65.51; H, 4.59; N, 16.09; S, 9.19%).

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Scheme 1

Scheme 2

where, R = (a) hydrogen, (b) 4-chloro, (c) 5-chloro, (d) 6-chloro, (e) 4-methyl, (f) 5-methyl, (g) 6-methyl

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of newly synthesized 1-naphthyl-2-hydrazino-1,3-benzothiazolylcarbamides **3(a-g)**

Compd.	Antibacterial ^a				Antifungal ^a	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
3a	16	14	18	24	26	12
3b	14	16	14	16	24	22
3c	20	16	24	18	26	24
3d	20	12	22	14	22	20
3e	16	14	24	26	26	22
3f	14	16	26	22	20	22
3g	18	12	22	24	22	24
Amikacin	25	23	25	26	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	28	26

^aIncluding the well diameter of 8 mm. Zone of inhibition in mm (15 or less) resistant, (16–20 mm) moderate and (more than 20 mm) sensitive.

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all compounds.

Antimicrobial studies :

All the compounds have been screen for both anti-

microbial and antifungal activity using cup plate agar diffusion method^{8,9} by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/mL using dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent.

Amikacin (100 µg/mL) was used as standard for antibacterial activity and Fluconazole (100 µg/mL) as standard for antifungal activity.

Conclusion

Derivatives were synthesized and characterized for their structure elucidation. Various chemical and spectral data supported the structures. Some of the compounds synthesized showed promising antimicrobial activities. The newly synthesized carbamides exhibits comparable antibacterial and antifungal activities against the organisms tested. The method adopted in this investigation is simple, efficient and inexpensive and is useful in synthesizing pharmacologically important molecules.

Antibacterial studies of these compounds indicated that compounds **3c** and **3d** were found to be active against *E. coli* and rest were found to be moderately active, **3c**, **3e**, **3f** and **3g** exhibited most significant activity against *Proteus vulgaris* and **3a**, **3e**, **3f** and **3g** towards *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All the other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity (Table 2).

The results of antifungal activities are also tabulated in Table 2. **3a**, **3b**, **3c** and **3e** are most effectively active against *Candida albicans*, **3b**, **3c**, **3e** and **3g** actively inhibited *Aspergillus niger*. While other compounds inhibited moderate activity.

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